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[COLDSPARK.EU](https://coldspark.eu)

PROJECT
#COLDSPARK

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Cold Methane
Pyrolysis

PROJECT COLDSPARK®

A novel approach to
ultra low carbon
hydrogen production
and high purity
elemental carbon
(eCarbon)®

With its high **oxidative stability** and **uniform crystalite size** ranging from 5 to 11 nm eCarbon® is an ideal choice for the production of battery electrode materials for lithium-ion batteries, supercapacitors, etc. ensuring efficiency and reliability.

The eCarbon®'s **curling and amorphous edges** serve as active reinforcement sites in **tyre production**, significantly enhancing the quality and performance of the final product.

eCarbon®'s is suitable for application in **soil modifiers** and as an additive to **agricultural mulch** films to augment its durability and resistance to UV radiation.

With high purity and particle size N220-330, eCarbon® is ideal for the production of car treads, conveyor belts, anti-vibration **rubber goods**, etc. Its properties make it an excellent additive in manufacturing **composite materials**, suitable for applications in flexible electronics and sensors.

eCarbon® is an ideal raw material for the **construction industry**, enabling the production of strong, **corrosion-resistant Carbon Rebar** as a substitute for traditional steel rebars.

eCarbon®'s properties allow its application in the **automotive sector** serving as both a pigment and UV stabiliser in coatings, including those for metal protection.

With high purity and **catalyst-free production via methane pyrolysis**, eCarbon® provides a **low CO₂** alternative to traditional coal, effectively meeting the steel industries environmental compliance needs.

eCarbon® is a patented product developed through the ColdSpark® project, representing a promising new technology that combines environmental friendliness with customisable operating conditions and low energy consumption. It is also producing valuable ultra-low carbon hydrogen as an additional output. Notably, the production of eCarbon® is free from NO_x and SO_x emissions, and the final product is highly pure with minimal moisture content.